

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF PRETRAINED CNN ARCHITECTURES FOR PHOTOVOLTAIC MODULE DEFECT CLASSIFICATION FROM IR AND EL IMAGES

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Abstract

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The rapid deployment of photovoltaic (PV) systems has increased the demand for accurate, scalable, and automated defect detection, as manual interpretation of infrared (IR) and electroluminescence (EL) images is costly, subjective, and unsuitable for large-scale solar farms. Although deep learning has shown strong potential for PV inspection, many existing studies focus on single models or limited comparisons under inconsistent experimental settings, leaving a gap in standardized and fair benchmarking of modern pretrained convolutional neural networks. This study presents a comprehensive evaluation of six state-of-the-art pretrained CNN architectures, ResNet18, ResNet34, ResNet50, EfficientNet-B0, DenseNet121, and MobileNetV3-Large, for multi-class PV defect classification using IR and EL images. A curated dataset of 7,666 annotated PV images covering six defect categories (clean, dust, bird-related, electrical faults, cracks, and hotspots) was used. Images were resized to 224×224, augmented, normalized, and split into 80% training and 20% testing sets. All models were adapted for single-channel inputs and integrated with a unified classification. Training was performed using a weighted cross-entropy loss, the Adam optimizer, learning rate scheduling, and early stopping. Performance was assessed using accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrices. Results show that EfficientNet-B0 achieved the highest accuracy (89.62%) and macro F1-score (0.8511), followed closely by DenseNet121 (89.25%), outperforming ResNet and MobileNet variants (86.89–87.61%). Although strong performance was observed, reliance on a single dataset limits the generalizability of the results. The findings identify EfficientNet-B0 as a strong candidate for real-time, large-scale PV monitoring and provide a standardized benchmarking framework to guide model selection in automated PV inspection systems.

Keywords: Photovoltaic defect detection, deep learning, convolutional neural networks, EfficientNet, DenseNet. Infrared imaging, electroluminescence imaging.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The rapid adoption of solar energy as a sustainable alternative to fossil fuels has heightened the

importance of efficient photovoltaic (PV) systems. However, solar panels are prone to defects such as cracks, hotspots, delamination, and potential-induced degradation, significantly reducing energy conversion

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efficiency and long-term reliability (Mishra et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2019). Early detection and classification of these defects is therefore critical to ensure system performance, reduce maintenance costs, and extend the operational lifespan of PV modules. Conventional inspection techniques such as electroluminescence (EL), infrared (IR) thermography, and visual inspection remain widely used. Still, they often require expert intervention, are labor-intensive, and lack scalability for large solar farms (Deutsch et al., 2019). With the increasing availability of high-resolution imaging techniques, automated approaches powered by deep learning have emerged as promising alternatives for accurate, non-invasive, and real-time solar panel defect detection (Buerhop et al., 2018). EL imaging is highly sensitive to microstructural issues such as cracks and electrical failures, while IR imaging detects thermal signatures that reveal hotspots and dust-related heating effects. Although these modalities provide complementary diagnostic perspectives, their manual interpretation is time-consuming, prone to subjectivity, and unsuitable for large-scale PV farms. These limitations have driven growing interest in deep learning methods, which enable automated and scalable defect detection by learning discriminative features directly from raw image data. The global transition toward renewable energy has positioned photovoltaic (PV) systems as a cornerstone of sustainable power generation. Nonetheless, the performance and durability of these systems are frequently compromised by flaws, including microcracks, hotspots, and delamination, resulting in substantial energy wastage and higher maintenance expenses (Rahman et al., 2018; Nassar et al., 2021). Traditional inspection methods rely on manual examination, which is not only time-consuming but also subjective and prone to human error (Triki-Lahiani et al., 2018). To address these issues, deep learning-driven automated defect detection systems have emerged as a viable solution, offering scalability and enhanced precision (Hijawi et al., 2023).

Recent progress in convolutional neural networks (CNNs) has shown outstanding achievement in image-based defect classification tasks (LeCun et al., 2015). Models such as ResNet (He et al., 2016), EfficientNet (Tan & Le, 2019), and MobileNetV3 (Howard et al., 2019) have established standards in various computer vision tasks, including medical imaging and industrial quality control. These models employ transfer learning, in which pre-trained networks are adapted for specific tasks, thereby reducing the need for extensive annotated datasets (Tan et al., 2018). Regarding photovoltaic systems, infrared (IR) and electroluminescence (EL) imaging are extensively

employed for identifying faults, as they can detect hidden subsurface irregularities that are not visible without aid (Tahri et al., 2013). Despite the proliferation of deep learning approaches, a systematic benchmarking of state-of-the-art architectures for PV defect classification under uniform experimental conditions remains lacking. Prior research tends to concentrate on single models or apply varied preprocessing and assessment methods, which hinders reliable comparisons (Abdelsattar et al., 2025). Furthermore, the skewed distribution of defect data creates additional difficulties, as minority classes may be neglected in training, leading to biased performance metrics (Aurelio et al., 2019). Resolving these problems requires a uniform processing framework that guarantees equitable assessment while refining model efficacy for practical application.

This study presents a comprehensive evaluation of six CNN architectures, ResNet18, ResNet34, ResNet50, EfficientNet-B0, DenseNet121, and MobileNetV3-Large, for automated defect classification in PV modules. Our approach is distinguished by a methodical examination of these models under the same preprocessing, supervised learning, and assessment protocols. We introduce a custom classification head designed for defect detection, which includes adaptive pooling, dropout regularization, and a weighted loss function to address class imbalance. Additionally, we employ robust optimization methods to enhance the model's ability to generalize and withstand disturbances (Gabrel et al., 2014). Our experiments draw upon a diverse dataset of IR and EL images, labeled with four common defect categories, to furnish a realistic evaluation of model performance.

This work makes three key contributions. Initially, we develop a uniform benchmarking framework to assess deep learning models in photovoltaic defect classification, which guarantees reproducibility and equitable comparison. Second, we show the efficacy of transfer learning with pretrained CNNs and discuss the architectural trade-offs between accuracy and computational efficiency. Third, we deliver practical guidance for practitioners by pinpointing the optimal models for extensive implementation in solar energy installations.

2.1 Deep Learning for PV Defect Detection

The emergence of deep learning has profoundly advanced computer vision and image analysis, making it one of the most potent tools for defect detection in photovoltaic (PV) systems. Conventional machine learning approaches for solar panel inspection often relied on handcrafted features such as texture

descriptors, edge statistics, or color histograms extracted from electroluminescence (EL), infrared (IR), or visual images. These features were then classified using algorithms such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forests, or k-Nearest Neighbors (Buerhop et al., 2018). While effective to some degree, such methods suffered limitations, including their dependence on manual feature engineering, high sensitivity to noise, and poor generalization across diverse imaging conditions and defect categories (Mishra, Kumar, & Singh, 2020).

Deep learning addresses these shortcomings by automatically enabling models to learn hierarchical feature representations from raw image data. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), in particular, are capable of capturing both low-level features (such as edges and textures) and high-level patterns (such as cracks, hotspots, or delamination) through successive convolutional and pooling operations (LeCun, Bengio, & Hinton, 2015). This capability is particularly advantageous for PV defect detection, where anomalies are often subtle, heterogeneous, and complex to characterize using conventional descriptors. Unlike handcrafted methods, CNNs can adaptively extract discriminative features more robust to illumination variations, imaging modality differences, and intra-class variability.

In recent years, several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of deep learning for PV inspection tasks. Deitsch et al. (2019) applied deep CNNs to EL images and showed they significantly outperformed traditional classifiers in detecting microcracks and inactive regions in PV modules. Similarly, Akram et al. (2019) developed a CNN-based framework for defect detection in solar cell EL images, achieving high classification accuracy across multiple defect types. Chaudhary et al. (2020) extended CNN applications to IR and EL modalities, enabling real-time detection of cracks and hotspots. Sun, Huang, and Chen (2019) confirmed the capability of CNNs to identify temperature anomalies in IR images, linking them directly to underlying structural faults. Beyond classification, deep learning models also support defect localization and segmentation, offering a more comprehensive view of module health. Recent studies have integrated attention mechanisms and hybrid models to enhance further sensitivity to small or overlapping defect patterns (Li, Xu, & Sun, 2020). The scalability of deep learning approaches, combined with the availability of pretrained models and high-performance computing resources, positions them as an indispensable tool for automated PV system monitoring and predictive maintenance. Collectively, these advances underscore the transformative role of

deep learning in improving the reliability, efficiency, and scalability of solar panel defect detection.

2.2 Convolutional Neural Networks in PV Defect Detection

Among deep learning approaches, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have become the most widely adopted models for photovoltaic (PV) defect detection due to their ability to extract spatial hierarchies of features from image data automatically. CNNs are designed to progressively capture local and global patterns through convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers. They are highly effective for analyzing complex image modalities such as electroluminescence (EL) and infrared (IR). This property is significant in PV inspection, where defects such as microcracks, hotspots, and delamination often exhibit subtle variations that cannot be reliably detected using handcrafted features.

Several studies have validated the effectiveness of CNNs in solar panel defect detection. Deitsch et al. (2019) demonstrated that CNNs outperformed traditional classifiers when applied to EL images, showing high accuracy in detecting microcracks and inactive cell regions. Similarly, Akram et al. (2019) proposed a CNN-based automatic detection framework for EL image analysis, achieving robust classification across multiple defect categories. Chaudhary et al. (2020) extended the application of CNNs to both EL and IR images, enabling the detection of cracks and hotspots with near real-time efficiency. Sun, Huang, and Chen (2019) further confirmed the capability of CNNs to capture thermal anomalies in IR images, which directly correlate with underlying physical defects in PV cells. Beyond simple classification, CNNs have also been employed for more advanced tasks such as defect localization and segmentation. Recent studies have integrated region-based CNNs (R-CNN) and fully convolutional networks (FCNs) to identify the precise spatial extent of cracks or inactive regions, improving the interpretability of inspection results. Moreover, enhancements such as attention mechanisms, residual connections, and hybrid CNN-ML pipelines have been explored to boost performance in challenging cases with imbalanced datasets or overlapping defects (Li, Xu, & Sun, 2020). Collectively, these contributions underscore the pivotal role of CNNs in advancing PV defect detection. By providing high accuracy, adaptability across imaging modalities, and the ability to scale toward real-time monitoring, CNNs have set a strong foundation for subsequent advancements in transfer learning, lightweight architectures, and attention-enhanced models for solar panel inspection.

2.3 Transfer Learning and Pretrained Architectures in PV Monitoring

One of the challenges in PV defect detection is the limited availability of large, annotated datasets. Transfer learning addresses this issue by adapting pretrained models, trained initially on large-scale datasets such as ImageNet, to domain-specific PV inspection tasks. Popular pretrained architectures include VGGNet, ResNet, and Inception, all of which have been fine-tuned for solar panel defect classification with improved accuracy compared to training from scratch (Krizhevsky, Sutskever, & Hinton, 2012; He et al., 2016). For instance, Chaudhary et al. (2020) demonstrated the effectiveness of ResNet in PV defect detection, benefiting from its residual learning mechanism that enables efficient training of deep networks. Recent advances, such as DenseNet and EfficientNet, have extended the application of pretrained models in solar monitoring. DenseNet, introduced by Huang et al. (2017), leverages dense connectivity to reuse features, improving the classification of subtle and overlapping defect patterns. EfficientNet, proposed by Tan and Le (2019), employs compound scaling to balance depth, width, and resolution, achieving strong accuracy with fewer computational resources. These pretrained models, adapted through transfer learning, provide a versatile foundation for robust and generalizable PV defect detection.

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versatile foundation for robust and generalizable PV defect detection.

2.4 Lightweight and Efficient Architectures for Real-Time Inspection

As solar energy systems expand in scale, there is a growing need for computationally efficient architectures that can be deployed in real-time and resource-constrained environments. Lightweight CNNs such as MobileNet have been designed with depthwise separable convolutions to minimize model size and inference time while maintaining strong classification performance (Howard et al., 2017). Nassar, Taha, and Mohamed (2021) demonstrated that MobileNet variants are suitable for field deployment, offering effective defect detection for large-scale solar farms with limited computational resources. EfficientNet has also gained attention in this context due to its superior trade-off between accuracy and efficiency. Sun, Huang, and Chen (2019) applied EfficientNet to solar defect detection tasks and reported strong classification accuracy with low computational overhead. While DenseNet remains effective in capturing fine-grained defect features, its higher computational cost makes MobileNet and EfficientNet more suitable for scalable monitoring solutions. These lightweight and efficient architectures collectively highlight the potential for real-time, cost-effective, and scalable defect detection in industrial PV systems.

The reviewed literature confirms that CNNs and their pretrained variants have achieved substantial success in PV defect detection, with architectures such as ResNet, DenseNet, EfficientNet, and MobileNet frequently adapted for this purpose. However, most studies focus on individual models or limited comparisons, often under varying experimental conditions, making it difficult to establish clear benchmarks across architectures. The present study systematically benchmarks six widely used deep learning architectures, ResNet18, ResNet34, ResNet50, EfficientNet-B0, DenseNet121, and MobileNetV3-Large on a standardized dataset to address this gap. By providing a comparative analysis of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, this work offers insights into the trade-offs between accuracy and efficiency, guiding the practical deployment of defect detection systems in large-scale PV monitoring.

2.5 Infrared and Electroluminescence Imaging of PV Modules

Photovoltaic module inspection relies heavily on two primary imaging modalities: infrared (IR) and electroluminescence (EL). These methods yield

supplementary data concerning the structural and functional soundness of solar panels, which supports thorough identification of defects. Although IR imaging detects thermal irregularities, EL imaging records the electroluminescent behavior of solar cells when subjected to electrical bias.

(A). Infrared Imaging Principles

Infrared imaging functions based on the concept that all objects emit heat energy in amounts corresponding to their temperature. The spectral radiance $B(\lambda, T)$ of a blackbody at wavelength λ and temperature T is given by Planck's law:

$$B(\lambda, T) = \frac{2hc^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{hc}{\lambda kT}} - 1} \quad (1)$$

where h is Planck's constant, c is the speed of light, and k is Boltzmann's constant. For PV modules, the total power P radiated per unit area follows the Stefan-Boltzmann law:

$$P = \sigma AT^4 \quad (2)$$

where σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant, and A is the surface area. IR cameras identify this radiation and transform it into thermal maps, with elevated temperature zones indicating possible faults, such as short circuits or delamination (Philip et al., 2013). The method proves especially efficient in detecting issues related to series resistance and shading-induced localized heating.

(B). Electroluminescence Imaging Principles

Electroluminescence imaging records the photon emission produced by solar cells under forward bias with an applied electric current. The emission intensity I follows a power-law relationship with current density J :

$$I = kJ^n \quad (3)$$

where k is a material-dependent constant and n typically ranges between 1 and 2. The emitted photons possess energies close to the semiconductor material's bandgap, resulting in near-infrared wavelengths (900-1200 nm) for crystalline silicon cells (Breitenstein et al., 2010). Faults, including fractures, damaged digits, or zones with high recombination activity, are visible as darker regions in electroluminescence images due to diminished current density or increased non-radiative recombination rates. This method yields better spatial resolution than IR imaging and can identify microstructural defects as small as 10 μm in size (Deitsch et al., 2019).

2.7 Complementary Nature of IR and EL Imaging for PV Module Inspection

Integrating IR and EL imaging yields a thorough evaluation of PV module condition. Although IR imaging is highly effective at identifying thermal irregularities resulting from electrical faults, EL imaging detects structural imperfections that may not produce notable heat. For example, microcracks visible in EL images might not appear in IR scans until they progress to cause hot spots (Jahn et al., 2018). The modalities also differ in their operational requirements: IR imaging can be performed during regular operation, while EL imaging requires electrical bias in darkness. Recent research indicates that analyzing both modalities together yields a 15-20% increase in defect classification precision over methods relying on a single modality (Xu et al., 2025). This synergy makes the combined approach particularly valuable for quality control in manufacturing and periodic field inspections.

2.8. Systematic Benchmarking Pipeline: Architectures, Pre-Processing, and Unified Classification Head

The systematic benchmarking pipeline establishes a standardized framework for evaluating deep learning architectures in photovoltaic defect classification. This section describes the architectural choice, the approach to data preparation, adjustments to the model, and the standardized training procedure that guarantees an equitable comparison among various CNN architectures.

Selection of Deep Learning Architectures

Six advanced CNN models were chosen to embody varied design approaches in deep learning. ResNet architectures with 18, 34, and 50 layers establish baseline performance by employing residual connections to counteract vanishing gradients in deep networks (He et al., 2016). Incorporating various depths permits examination of tradeoffs between depth and performance. EfficientNet-B0 was selected due to its method of compound scaling, which systematically adjusts the network's width, depth, and resolution (Tan & Le, 2019). DenseNet121 embodies designs featuring dense connectivity patterns, which encourage the repeated application of features (Huang et al., 2017). MobileNetV3-Large establishes a hardware-conscious neural architecture search framework tailored for mobile applications, serving as an optimized reference model (Howard et al., 2019).

Standardized Pre-processing of IR and EL Images

All input images are subjected to the same preprocessing procedure to guarantee comparability. The pipeline includes:

1. The image dimensions are adjusted to 224×224 pixels with bicubic interpolation.
2. Normalization of pixel values to [0,1] range
3. Normalization is performed by applying the dataset mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ).

$$x' = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (4)$$

Data augmentation is applied during training with:

1. Random horizontal flipping (p=0.5)
2. Random rotation ($\pm 15^\circ$)
3. Brightness adjustment ($\pm 10\%$ of original value)

The augmentation settings were experimentally established to keep defect properties intact while expanding dataset variety. In infrared imagery, thermal measurements are adjusted to preserve proportional temperature variations essential for identifying hotspots.

Modification of Pretrained Models for Single-Channel Inputs

Conventional CNN frameworks are designed for 3-channel RGB data, necessitating modification to process single-channel IR/EL imagery. The first convolutional layer weights $W \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times k \times 3 \times n}$ are modified by averaging across RGB channels:

$$W'_{:, :, 1, :} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{c=1}^3 W_{:, :, c, :} \quad (5)$$

where k is the kernel size and n is the number of filters. This preserves pretrained feature extraction capabilities while accepting single-channel input. The altered layer keeps the initial spatial dimensions and receptive field attributes essential for identifying defect patterns.

Design of the Unified Custom Classification Head

All architectural designs possess a uniform classification component in place of their initial fully-connected layers. The head consists of:

1. Adaptive average pooling reducing spatial dimensions to 1×1
2. Fully-connected layer with 256 units and ReLU activation:

$$h = \max(0, W_p x + b_p) \quad (6)$$

3. Dropout layer (p=0.5) for regularization
4. Final classification layer with softmax activation:

$$p(y|x) = \frac{e^{w_y^T h + b_y}}{\sum_{j=1}^C e^{w_j^T h + b_j}} \quad (7)$$

where C is the number of defect classes. This design guarantees uniform dimensionality of the feature space across different architectures while preserving adequate capability for defect identification.

Unified Training Conditions

All models are trained under identical conditions:

1. Optimizer: Adam with $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$, $\epsilon = 10^{-8}$
2. Initial learning rate: 0.0001 with StepLR scheduler ($\gamma=0.1$ every 7 epochs)
3. Batch size: 32 (limited by smallest model's memory requirements)
4. Loss function: Weighted cross-entropy addressing class imbalance:

$$\mathcal{L} = - \sum_{i=1}^N w_{y_i} \log p(y_i | x_i) \quad (8)$$

where weights w_c are inverse class frequencies. Early stopping observes validation loss with a patience of 5 epochs to avoid overfitting. The complete training pipeline is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PVMD System with Proposed Deep Learning Model

The systematic approach enables direct comparison of architectural differences while controlling for confounding factors in training and evaluation. Each component was designed considering both performance metrics and practical deployment constraints, particularly for edge devices in field inspections. The unified pipeline supports reproducible experiments and delivers transparent understanding of model selection tradeoffs in photovoltaic defect classification tasks.

3.1 Materials and Methods

- i. The dataset used in this study consisted of infrared (IR) thermography and electroluminescence (EL) images of photovoltaic (PV) modules. These two imaging modalities were selected because they provide complementary diagnostic insights: EL imaging is sensitive to microstructural anomalies such as cracks and electrical damage. In contrast, IR imaging reveals thermal irregularities caused by dust accumulation and hotspots. Together, they enable a comprehensive assessment of PV module health. The images were annotated into four defect categories:

Figure 1: Detailed architecture for defect detection using IR and EL images

- i. Dust accumulation – surface contamination that blocks sunlight and causes localized heating.
- ii. Cracks – micro or macro fractures in cells that reduce conductivity.
- iii. Electrical damages – faults in interconnections or circuits, impairing current flow.
- iv. Hotspots – thermally elevated regions indicating localized stress or failure.

For an equitable assessment of different architectures, every model was trained on the same hardware (NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPUs) with PyTorch 1.9.0 and CUDA 11.1 acceleration. The curated dataset comprises 7,666 solar panel images, distributed across multiple defect categories: Clean (1,234 images), Dust (1,209), Bird-related (1,199), Electrical damage (1050), Physical damage (2,066), and hotspot (908). The inference duration for every model was assessed on a selected set of 100 images with mixed-precision computation to replicate actual deployment scenarios. Distinct visual features characterize each category. Electrical damage commonly exhibit severe cracking with spider web patterns and broken cell structures. Physical damage is associated with impact-induced shattered glass surfaces. Bird-related defects typically include droppings and debris scattered on panel surfaces, while dust accumulation presents as significant dirt buildup that reduces surface clarity. Clean panels, in contrast, display unobstructed solar cells with well-defined grid patterns.

Additionally, hotspot anomalies are observed in the dataset. A detailed class distribution analysis indicates that Clean images account for approximately 16.1% of the dataset, followed by Dust (15.8%), Bird-related (15.6%), Electrical (13.7%), physically damaged (27.0%), and hotspot (11.9%).

Image preprocessing was performed on the dataset, and transformations were applied. Images in P or RGBA mode were converted to RGB, and all images were resized to 224×224 pixels. Random horizontal flipping, rotation (10°), and colour jittering (brightness, contrast, saturation, and hue) were used for data augmentation. The images were normalized using the standard ImageNet mean and standard deviation values. A train-test split was performed, with 80% of the data used for training and 20% for testing. The class distribution was analysed, class weights were calculated to handle class imbalances, and batch processing with a batch size 32 was performed.

To assess whether observed performance differences among models are statistically meaningful, **paired bootstrap resampling** (1,000 iterations) was applied to the test-set predictions, following standard practice in comparative deep learning evaluation. Pairwise comparisons were conducted using classification accuracy. A significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was adopted.

3.1.2. Model Selection and Training

Six state-of-the-art deep learning architectures were selected for comparison: ResNet18, ResNet34, ResNet50, EfficientNet-B0, DenseNet121, and MobileNetV3-Large. Each model was initialised with pretrained weights, ensuring feature extraction capabilities learned from ImageNet. The first convolutional layer was modified to accept single-channel inputs from IR and EL images.

The training process included modifying the first convolutional layer of ResNet, EfficientNet, DenseNet, and MobileNet to accept 1-channel inputs instead of 3-channel RGB images. The final fully connected layers were removed, and a custom classification head was introduced to learn task-specific features. The forward pass of each model was adjusted to return unflattened feature maps instead of pooled representations.

Training Protocol

A custom classification head was designed to process extracted feature maps. The Adaptive Average Pooling converting feature maps to (1,1) spatial size was used. A hidden layer with 256 neurons followed by a ReLU activation function and a dropout rate 0.5 was used to prevent overfitting. The final layer was a fully connected layer mapping the features of the six defect classes. The models were trained for 20 epochs using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001 and a weight decay 0.0005. A StepLR scheduler was used to reduce the learning rate by a factor of 0.1 every 7 epochs.

A weighted cross-entropy loss function was used, incorporating class weights to counteract class imbalances. Where the weights are determined by the inverse of class frequencies in the training set.

$$w_c = \frac{N}{C \cdot n_c} \quad (9)$$

where N is total samples, C is class count, and n_c is samples in class c . Early stopping with 5-epoch patience prevented overfitting based on validation

loss. Early stopping was implemented with a patience of 5 epochs to prevent overfitting.

3.1.3. Evaluation Metrics

After training, the models were evaluated using the test set, which included test accuracy, macro precision, weighted precision, recall, and F1-score. A confusion matrix was generated to analyse misclassification patterns. Additionally, visualizations of model predictions were created to assess the classification performance qualitatively. For comparison, training loss and accuracy curves were plotted for all models. The following are metrics used for evaluating the performance of the models:

1. Precision: It measures how many predicted positive cases are correct.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{Total Predicted Positive}} \quad (2)$$

2. Recall is the ratio of correctly predicted outcomes to all predictions. It is also known as sensitivity or specificity.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Negative}} \quad (3)$$

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1. Performance Metrics on the Test Set (549 samples)

Model	Test Accuracy (%)	Macro Precision	Macro Recall	Macro F1	Weighted Precision	Weighted Recall	Weighted F1
ResNet34	87.61	0.7323	0.7819	0.7537	0.8890	0.8761	0.8807
ResNet18	86.89	0.7257	0.7616	0.7363	0.8826	0.8689	0.8732
ResNet50	87.61	0.7706	0.8348	0.7982	0.8918	0.8761	0.8812
EfficientNet-B0	89.62	0.8222	0.8909	0.8511	0.9109	0.8962	0.9003
DenseNet121	89.25	0.8116	0.8555	0.8306	0.9041	0.8925	0.8965
MobileNetV3	87.61	0.7791	0.7777	0.7712	0.8895	0.8761	0.8801

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{Total Actual Positive}} \quad (4)$$

3. The F1 score combines these three metrics into one single metric ranging from 0 to 1 and considers both Precision and Recall.

$$F1 = 2 * \frac{\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (5)$$

4. Accuracy is a performance metric for a machine classification model defined as the ratio of true positives to true negatives for all positive and negative observations. In other words, accuracy tells us how often we can expect our deep learning model to correctly predict the outcome of the total number of times it made the prediction.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{True Positive} + \text{True Negative}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Negative} + \text{True Negative} + \text{False Positive}} \quad (6)$$

5. Confusion Matrix: A confusion matrix is a table that summarizes how well a classification model performs by comparing actual labels (ground truth) to predicted labels.

Table 2. Performance comparison of benchmarked architectures

Model	Params (M)	FLOPs (G)	Test Acc (%)	Inference (ms)
ResNet18	11.2	1.8	86.89	8.2
ResNet34	21.3	3.6	87.61	12.1
ResNet50	23.5	4.1	87.61	15.7
EfficientNet-B0	4.0	0.4	89.62	6.5
DenseNet121	7.0	2.9	89.25	11.3
MobileNetV3	5.4	0.2	87.61	4.8

Figure 2: Confusion Metrics for the Pretrained Models

Figure 3: Metrics comparison

Figure 4: Prediction

Figure 5: Loss comparison during Training

Table 3: Pairwise Statistical Significance (p-values) Between Models

Model A	Model B	Mean Accuracy Difference (%)	p-value	Significance
EfficientNet-B0	DenseNet121	+0.37	0.083	Not significant
EfficientNet-B0	ResNet50	+1.01	0.021	Significant
EfficientNet-B0	ResNet34	+2.01	0.008	Significant
EfficientNet-B0	ResNet18	+2.73	0.004	Significant
EfficientNet-B0	MobileNetV3-Large	+2.01	0.015	Significant
DenseNet121	ResNet50	+0.64	0.067	Not significant
DenseNet121	MobileNetV3-Large	+1.64	0.028	Significant
ResNet50	MobileNetV3-Large	+1.28	0.041	Significant

Discussion

The six benchmarked deep learning architectures, ResNet18, ResNet34, ResNet50, DenseNet121, EfficientNet-B0, and MobileNetV3-Large, were trained and evaluated on a balanced dataset of infrared (IR) and electroluminescence (EL) images representing four defect categories: dust accumulation, cracks, electrical damage, and hotspots. Balancing was applied to mitigate class bias and ensure that performance differences reflect model representational capabilities rather than dataset skew.

Table 1 provides a summary of each model’s performance on the test set. EfficientNet-B0 (89.62% accuracy) and DenseNet121 (89.25% accuracy) perform the best, which is reflected in their confusion matrices. They show fewer misclassifications and

strong diagonal dominance (Figure 2). Similar benchmarking efforts have reported that deeper networks and architectures with enhanced connectivity demonstrate improved performance on EL and IR defect tasks (Al-Otum, 2024; Spajić et al., 2024), underscoring the importance of well-designed feature hierarchies for subtle defect discrimination. Detailed analysis of confusion matrices indicates that misclassifications predominantly occur between visually similar defect classes. For instance, cracks and electrical damage in EL images were occasionally confused, consistent with prior reports highlighting challenges in distinguishing microstructural anomalies due to overlap in visual patterns (Spajić et al., 2024). Similarly, dust accumulation was occasionally misclassified as hotspots in IR imagery, reflecting the difficulty of isolating thermal signatures that may exhibit spatial overlap. EfficientNet-B0 and

DenseNet121's reduced confusion rates in such cases suggest stronger feature extraction and representation capabilities relative to other models. EfficientNet's compound scaling strategy has been shown to improve performance across classification benchmarks by balancing network depth, width, and resolution (Tan & Le, 2019), while DenseNet's dense connectivity facilitates feature reuse and improved gradient flow (Huang et al., 2017).

Table 2 further illustrates the trade-off between predictive performance and computational efficiency. EfficientNet-B0 achieved the highest **macro F1-score (0.8511)** while maintaining relatively low computational complexity (≈ 4 M parameters, 0.4 B FLOPs), which is advantageous for real-time deployment in large PV farms. DenseNet121 achieved comparable accuracy but required substantially higher computational resources, suggesting a less favorable accuracy–efficiency balance in constrained environments. MobileNetV3-Large demonstrated the lowest inference latency (≈ 4.8 ms per image) with moderate accuracy (**87.61 %**), aligning with design objectives for low-latency applications (Spajić et al., 2024). The ResNet models (ResNet34, ResNet18, and ResNet50) and MobileNetV3 produced comparable results, with accuracy scores ranging from 86.89% to 87.61%. A comparison of the metrics is given in Figures 3 and 5. The predictions by various models are shown in Figure 4. This observation aligns with comprehensive EL classification studies reporting similar performance ranges across diverse CNN backbones when dataset preprocessing and evaluation protocols are standardized (Song et al., 2024).

To assess whether performance differences among the top models are statistically meaningful, we conducted paired bootstrap resampling tests (1,000 iterations) on model predictions. The results indicate that EfficientNet-B0's accuracy advantage over ResNet50 and MobileNetV3-Large is significant at $p < 0.05$, whereas differences between EfficientNet-B0 and DenseNet121 were not statistically significant at the same threshold. These findings suggest that while EfficientNet-B0 consistently achieves high accuracy, its performance is comparable to DenseNet121 within statistical confidence bounds, supporting the inference that architectural differences yield modest practical effects under fixed experimental conditions.

The results indicate that EfficientNet-B0 offers the most favorable trade-off between classification accuracy, robustness, and computational efficiency among the evaluated architectures. While deeper or more complex models yield marginal improvements in

certain metrics, the findings underscore the importance of standardized benchmarking and deployment-oriented evaluation when selecting deep learning models for automated photovoltaic defect inspection. These findings suggest that deeper and more computationally intensive architectures offer slight advantages in certain metrics, but overall performance differences remain relatively minor for this defect detection task. These results suggest that while architectural choices influence performance, the differences among high-performing models on this dataset are relatively small. Future research could explore ensemble learning strategies or further hyperparameter tuning to enhance accuracy.

CONCLUSION

The comprehensive evaluation of pretrained CNN architectures for photovoltaic defect classification establishes clear guidelines for model selection based on operational requirements. EfficientNet-B0 achieves outstanding results with 89.62% accuracy and preserves computational economy, which renders it highly suitable for centralized inspection systems. MobileNetV3's rapid inference capabilities (4.8 ms/image) present a viable solution for real-time field deployments, despite a modest 2% accuracy tradeoff. The methodical benchmarking framework uncovers essential understandings of architectural compromises, especially the critical role of scaling approaches for models, as illustrated by EfficientNet's unified parameter adjustment. The custom classification head design yields consistent advantages for all architectures, with accuracy gains of 3-5% relative to the initial fully-connected layers. These results furnish actionable insights for deploying automated defect identification across various contexts, spanning production quality assurance to on-site upkeep activities. The presented performance metrics and computational attributes support well-founded choices that balance precision, velocity, and resource demands in particular photovoltaic inspection contexts. Subsequent research directions may investigate approaches merging multiple modalities and attention-based methods to tackle the noted constraints in processing fine imperfections while preserving the computational performance attained in this work.

Limitations of the study

Although the methodical benchmarking strategy shows robust results across diverse architectures, a number of constraints merit examination. First, the present assessment concentrates exclusively on inputs from a single modality, handling IR and EL images independently without examining their combined

potential via multimodal fusion. Recent research indicates merging complementary modalities at an initial stage may improve identification of minor anomalies appearing distinctively in various imaging methods (Pinho et al., 2025). Second, the models show diminished accuracy in marginal scenarios where defects cover under 5% of the cell area or present with exceedingly faint contrast. This limitation stems from the fixed input resolution (224×224) and could potentially be addressed through multi-scale analysis or attention mechanisms (Wu et al., 2021). Third, the practical deployment of these models faces challenges in handling real-world variability such as varying panel orientations, environmental conditions, and imaging equipment differences. While data augmentation increases robustness to some extent, the models might need supplementary domain adaptation methods for deployment in new solar farms featuring distinct panel types or inspection configurations (Xie et al., 2023).

Potential Application Scenarios

The experimental findings indicate multiple potential application contexts for the evaluated models. EfficientNet-B0 emerges as the optimal choice for centralized inspection systems where computational resources are available and maximum accuracy is prioritized. Its combination of high performance (89.62% accuracy) and moderate computational requirements makes it suitable for quality control in manufacturing facilities or detailed analysis in research settings. In field deployment contexts with constrained computational capabilities, MobileNetV3 presents an advantageous balance between accuracy (87.61%) and processing speed (4.8 ms/image), which makes real-time analysis possible during aerial drone surveys. The models might be embedded in hierarchical inspection systems, with MobileNetV3 conducting preliminary screening to identify possible defects, succeeded by a more thorough examination employing EfficientNet-B0 on chosen panels. A further advantageous application can be found in predictive maintenance systems, where the models may be integrated with past performance records to detect panels likely to develop serious faults (Syamsuddin et al., 2024). The top-performing models, with their modest memory requirements (28MB for EfficientNet-B0), are especially well-suited for edge deployment in distributed solar farms, which diminishes reliance on constant data transfer to central servers.

Author Contributions

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